

HOW TO TEACH NEW METHODS EFFECTIVELY IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract: The article aims using new methods effectively in primary schools. To learn critical thinking of pupil making integratsion way to study methods and theme during the lesson. Students should learn tasks together teacher could create interrelated atmosphere among students.

Key words: technology, new method, integratsion, analytical, student -centred approach, montessory, personalized learning, flipped classroom.

Introduction: Method has been providing world-class design services to recognized brands around the world. But also which is new creatively ways for teachers. We use new methods technology necessary things for primary schools .During lesson teacher should use new methods for interested in learning for pupils . Primary school teachers play an important role in imparting knowledge to their students and keeping their classrooms engaged. Depending on the age of the children they teach and the subject they deliver, teachers can use different teaching styles to help their students learn.

Methods of analysis: Nowadays, most of hight level of teachers use different teaching methods, approach to teach students. We know that these are more effective for students during the lesson. Understanding some of the popular teaching styles for primary school can help you decide which method you might prefer to use when working in this field.

Literature analysis: In this article, we explain what teaching methods are, provide eight examples of teaching styles primary teachers commonly use and share the benefits of understanding a range of different methods. Teaching methods are techniques that teachers use to deliver information and help students achieve their learning outcomes. While there are several teaching styles, each one has a different way of engaging students and helping them master the lesson content. What teaching method works best for a student can depend on their educational background and learning abilities.⁶⁹ Teachers can adjust their methods to help students maintain focus, to manage student behaviour or to encourage active participation in group learning activities. Some subjects may be more suitable for various methods than others. For example, you may use project-based learning for students to explore ideas on building a new playground for their school. This project can help children explore the use of geometric shapes and their simple maths skills to add up the costs involved. This can offer children a great way to apply their knowledge to real-world scenarios.

EFFECTIVE TEACHING METHODS:

Small group instruction: Small group instruction provides children with a learning experience in a small group with their teacher. Providing lessons with this teaching method usually involves planning activities for students to rotate between to give them opportunities to work on a variety of tasks. This method allows teachers to pay close attention to each student's abilities and engage them in the learning activity. Engaging with students in a small group can be a great way to reinforce things learnt in a larger group and a way to encourage students to ask and answer questions with more confidence.

Teacher centred approach: This is one of the most common methods of primary school teaching. It usually involves the teacher being in charge of the classroom and directing all the learning activities while the students passively absorb the information. This method generally requires students to sit at individual desks while the teacher explains the topics. The teacher typically aims to minimise group work and rather assigns work individually to assess student progress. To learning allows students to be included in lesson planning and their learning process.⁷⁰

Student centred(constructivity)

This method provides children with the ability to develop their critical thinking skills while they interpret how to apply the knowledge they learn in the real world without the teacher directly instructing them. Unlike the teacher-centred approach,

⁶⁹ ."Future learn local Press" Published on October .Pages 32,36

⁷⁰ ."Future learn local Press" Published on October .Pages 32,36

students generally move around the classroom freely to explore their learning environment, with teachers taking a less active role in hosting the lessons. This teaching method can place a lot of responsibility and ownership on the students rather than on the teacher⁷¹.

Project-based learning: process provides an opportunity for children to develop their critical thinking abilities along with their analytical, research and teamwork skills. With this method of teaching, children usually work in small groups to complete projects based on an open-ended question the teacher provides. The aim of the project is usually to help children understand real-life problems and to see how their work can affect others. Project-based learning may include creating a campaign to encourage families within the school to recycle containers and then taking the containers to the recycling centre to learn about the recycling.

Montessori method

Using of offers a student-centred approach to learning for kindergartens and pre-primary students. With this teaching style, teachers usually set up the classroom with multiple learning activities and the children explore each activity at their own pace. The teacher may encourage students to explore a specific activity to ensure they experience a sufficient range of activities within each lesson. Rather than focussing on basic maths and literacy skills like most curriculum-based concepts, Montessori also teaches children life skills, including cleaning and cooking.

Inquiry based learning: This teaching style holds students responsible for their own learning. It encourages students to ask questions to allow them to explore and understand real-life experiences by reviewing material and sharing ideas with one another. Inquiry-based learning promotes problem-solving by providing students with the opportunity to fail at an activity and seek ways to improve their performance. This style of learning can be great to help students solve maths puzzles in their own unique way or to conduct their own science experiments to understand a concept in physics.⁷²

One of the best teaching methods are Flipped classroom and personalized learning and their different

Flipped learning is a newer method of teaching where teachers provide learning content online for children to learn at home. They then bring the students into the classroom to review the content and host discussions to see how they understand it. The aim of this method is to provide more time for active learning when the students are in the classroom, rather than the teacher using the time to deliver instruction

⁷¹ . Burkhanova M.G. (2021). Socio-philosophical look of a cultural man. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 12 (104), 422-425.

⁷² . Burkhanova M.G. (2021). Socio-philosophical look of a cultural man. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 12 (104), 422-425.

.Flipped classrooms can be more common amongst high school students who are competent in using a computer and want to learn at their own pace.

Personalized learning :Offering a personalised approach to teaching is a student-centred method. This method sees the teacher observing and responding to individual student strengths and weaknesses. The teacher typically spends a lot of time planning activities and learning outcomes for individual students based on how they learn best. By providing a personalised learning approach, teachers give their students the opportunity to develop their intellectual and creative talents at their own pace.⁷³

A teacher's professional behaviour, including supporting colleagues and talking with parents, also had a moderate impact on students' learning. The report said that there may not be a direct link with these practices and student achievement, but to capture a broad definition of good teaching they should be included. Effective professional learning for effective teaching has seven core attributes, which Learning Forward has defined as Standards for Professional Learning . Professional learning that doesn't include these attributes is unlikely to produce the same high level of results for educators and their students that effective professional learning will. (See the full list of the Standards for Professional Learning below.) A common attribute of effective schools is collaboration among educators. Engagement in one or more learning communities provides teachers opportunities to moderate their practice and expectations with their peers, to examine and reflect on their work together, to learn from one another, to challenge one another professionally, and to solve complex problems within the context of their unique work environment. Learning communities generate collective responsibility and accountability for effective teaching and student learning and engage teachers in school-based, ongoing learning focused on strengthening teachers' day-to-day practice and reducing variation in the effectiveness of teaching from classroom to classroom within a school so that every student, regardless of his or her classroom, experiences the same high level of teaching each day. In addition to leadership, successful schools and school systems invest resources to support effective teaching. Some of these resources include time for professional learning and collaboration, classroom and school-based support in the form of coaching, technology to seek information, models, networks, and research, and access to external experts who provide specialized knowledge and skill development when the needed expertise is unavailable within the school or district. The effects of these resource investments can be measured in increased student achievement. Measures of increased effectiveness in teaching and student achievement depend on the use of formative and summative assessments that provide data about teaching performance

⁷³ „Career Guide ” . Newspaper published 3 August Pages 60 66

and student achievement. These data plus data gleaned from examining student work and engagement, individual and collaborative teacher reflection, coaching, and other forms of peer interactions provide both informal and formal data that inform decisions related to improving teaching.⁷⁴

These data also provide information to link results for students with changes in teaching practices. Without a regular stream of data about multiple variables related to effective teaching and student learning, teachers, their peers, and supervisors lack valid, reliable, and tangible evidence about effective teaching. These data provide a continuous stream of information against which teachers benchmark their progress and continuous improvement. Because of the significance of data in teaching and professional learning, effective teaching requires extensive assessment literacy and skill in using data to identify, plan, and measure the effects of ongoing professional learning.

5. Conclusion

This study concluded that children need hands-on activities to engage in their own learning. Concrete materials help them understand and process the meaning. Teachers provide a range of activities to get young learners' attention and arouse constant interest. There is no "best" method of teaching. However, many researchers today agree that including more student-centered learning approaches in the classroom can improve learning. Using only a teacher-centered approach leaves out many skills and learning opportunities for students.

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